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STUDY ON THE SUSTAINABILITY AND MANAGEMENT OF MANAGEMENT OF SMALL HOTELS: IN RELATION TO THE ENVIRONMENT IN CALDAS NOVAS (GO), FROM 2015 TO 2020

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ABSTRACT

The present work brings about the management and its relationship with the environment in the years 2015 to 2020 of the inns in Caldas Novas, which is a municipality of Goiás that has a very high economic development driven by the growth of the large urban centers of the state. Naturally, this locality mixes local customs and, thought, mainly, in the form of organization of the tourist places, that is, appropriation of the urban spaces, mainly, population. It is possible to state that, through the modernization engendered in capitalist production, this territory has had a tourist dynamic that, due to this, managers have difficulties that cause the visible and disturbing impact in this region. The general objective is to analyze the management and its relationship with the environment in the years 2015 to 2020 of the inns in Caldas Novas. While the methodology is of a qualitative and quantitative approach, based on bibliographical, documentary and field research, using resources from books, articles, magazines, theses, dissertations, legislation, among other materials on Caldas Novas, found at the base of the Google Scholar and publications site related to the topic. As for the results, the surveys had their objectives achieved, showing that tourist activities and the management of inns have great responsibilities in the environmental impacts, based on the analyzes raised in these sectors. Finally, it is concluded that the constant significant increase of visitors, in Caldas Novas, causes the inns to be overcrowded, overloading their basic services, noting that this floating population starts to provide an increase in demand that results in the degradation local. However, it is summarized that tourist activities directly affect this municipality, harming the daily lives of residents of this city, considering that the management of these establishments is primarily responsible for negative experiences in this territory.

Keyword: Caldas Novas. Inn. Management. Environment..

INTRODUCTION

Caldas Novas is a municipality in the State of Goiás that has a high economic development, as shown by numbers exposed in IBGE (2023), driven by the growth of the state's large urban centers. Naturally, this locality mixes local customs and, thought, mainly, in the form of organization of the tourist places, that is, appropriation of the urban spaces, mainly, population.

It is possible to state that, through the modernization engendered in capitalist production, this territory has had a tourist dynamic that, due to this, managers have difficulties in adapting to compliance with environmental legislation in view of the progress on the rise, which causes the impact in that region.

Two factors contributed greatly to the settlement of the region: the thermal waters and gold that was plentiful on the banks of the stream of caldas, at the time called stream of lavras. Enthusiastic with the source of hot water, Martinho Coelho took up residence there, also keeping an eye on the gold mines that were multiplying: he took over a vast tract of land in the locality and built Sítio das Caldas, then requested the sesmaria (right of possession) of the lands, legalizing their properties, where he dedicated himself to gold mining. Soon the news of the existence of gold and the medicinal value of the waters spread, attracting hundreds of outsiders and sick people, who built shacks on the banks of the stream of lavras (JESUS, 2016, p. 02).

In view of this, the tourist activities of Caldas Novas began to gain new reflections by constituting spaces with greater emphasis on diversities that vary from the main attractions of leisure, education and recreation, such as, for example, the Parque Estadual da Serra that in the last 50 years expose a reality with activities related to ecotourism (SANTOS; BARBOSA; MENDONÇA, 2020).

Therefore, the main objective of the study is to understand the relationship between the problem and the relationship between the management of local-based inns in Caldas Novas and the incidence of problems caused to the environment in the years 2015 to 2020 and the way in which these can

respond to the demands current.

The article starts from the elementary assumption whose basis is structured in the bibliographical review aimed at explaining and understanding the performance with regard to the protection of the environment, its correlated legislation with support from field research. The central axis of the dissertation focuses on the expectation of receptivity of these norms and the impact on the structure of the family bonded inn, more traditional in Caldas Novas/GO.

The premise of the research rests on the justification of the permanence or not of these establishments by environmental dictates, in view of the emergence of large tourist complexes that offer better conditions and visibility to attract tourists from different regions of the country. At this point, small inns have more difficulties, as they are more restricted to the surrounding public, unknown nationwide. This difficulty has to be revisited in order to understand whether the core business of the commercial establishment can or cannot survive in the face of the currently imposed guidelines.

However, all tourist dynamics and the high investment destined for economic production cause changes in urban spaces, since all this represents visible impacts in Caldas Novas, which, due to tourist attractions, results in a high potential for the exploitation of natural resources. . Nevertheless, it is noted that population growth resides in urban spaces, presenting new behaviors that began to show themselves in demographic transformations and, thus, new forms of landscapes, in particular, the local environment.

PRESENTATION OF DATA SURVEYS

Descriptive, bibliographical and field research with a quantitative approach. The data collection instrument will be done through the application of a questionnaire with the managers of the inns in the main thermal tourist destination of the cerrado.

The sample was non-probabilistic. As inclusion criteria, it was composed of representatives (owner or manager) of inns in the city of Caldas Novas (GO), who participated in the 2019 Hotel Census. Exclusion criteria will include representatives of

inns who do not sign the TCLE.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

It was asked if there was knowledge of the execution of tourist projects whose purpose is to integrate the local community and the tourism activity and the answers were presented as follows: 11 (eleven) participants claimed to have no knowledge, only 2 (two) claimed to have knowledge and 4 (four) refused to participate in the research, totaling 17 (seventeen) as informed in the previous item.

According to Santos et. al., (2020), in Caldas Novas/GO, there are numerous tourist activities throughout the year, in which it could create tourist projects, contemplating, through resources, the expansion of the offer of local attractions that favor the integration of the local community, in order to generate more jobs, income and regional development. Above all, it has been perceived that this region has a demand that expands several sectors that are linked to tourism, such as, for example, restaurants, inns, among others, which are indirectly supplying the needs of the economic segment of this region. Therefore, it is necessary to develop planning through public will, private initiative and civil society itself.

It was asked if the inn participated in any promotion aimed at protecting the tourist, artistic and historical heritage of the municipality of Caldas Novas and it was possible to verify that 7 (seven) participants said they participated and 5 (five) said they did not participate and the others, refused to answer.

Complementing this question and the responses of the interviewees, it is clear that the relationship with the research comes from the precariousness of the promotion and destruction of the inns that, with the emergence of large complexes, did not follow the evolution of time and legal regulations:

People from outside started building inns, the natives started selling their land, handing over the land to them, and the movement grew and then for that reason it harmed the traditional people of the place a lot, because they

were taking up space. [Tourism started to arrive here when?] Tourism based on about 8 years when it started to grow tourism here; then they found out that the place was beautiful, that the people were preserving a lot and they started to arrive. Then these people from outside, the businessmen, started to create an eye and started building inns and then the people started to lose their tradition, their rights, so tourism in that sense is a little detrimental. Because the following: before we did the tourism in these small boats, with canoes, on the river, earning their money, selling something that was better sold on the coast, the tourists sought out the native people more, so we made money with that. And not now. There are the inns and they stay there, with their packages, they already do their things there, directly at the inns. So tourists don't leave anything with families. They stay there, what they have to drink they drink there, what they have to eat they eat there at the inns. Boat trips, the inns already have a boat to go on trips, so people are selling [...] (TURISMO EM FOCO, 2019, p. 50-51).

In line with the author's citation, this report was based on a response to the interviewees' narratives. Seeking, in this way, to prove that most inns do not participate in the protection of the tourist, artistic and historical heritage of the municipality of Caldas Novas, allowing reflections that reinforce the lack of environmental protection in this municipality (TURISMO EM FOCO, 2019).

Then, it was asked if the local tourism bodies value the didactics of having criteria to configure the smart destination. In view of this statement, the following options were presented: Totally Agree, Moderately Agree, Totally Disagree, Moderately Disagree and Undecided. The answers given are presented according to graph.

Graph Intelligent Tourist Destinations of Caldas Novas in the year 2022

Source: Data from the researcher (2022).

Observing the responses in the graph above, it is noted that there is greater agreement for an intelligent destination of some pillars. According to Santos et. al. (2021), Caldas Novas and Rio Quente need joint actions to improve tourism in these regions, not least because these cities have a range of tourist practices, where they attract a lot of tourists, therefore, to integrate this mission, it is necessary to have knowledge and a relationship of planning, private and public partnerships, respecting the difference of these places, however, these regions list a great need for conservation so that there is a positive potential in the results of economic growth.

In the following question, we asked if the inn participated in any project with the tourism department in the years 2015 to 2020 and, as in the answers given, we can verify that only one inn stated that it had participated.

In line with the answers, “the collective participation in the formulation of plans and projects contributes to the strengthening of local development, resulting in benefits for all involved”

(TURISMO EM FOCO, 2019, p. 21), in which it brings the prospect of reducing inequalities for a search for economic and social equity.

Continuing the next question asked how often this inn had participated during the period from 2015 to 2020, in response, only once.

In view of this, Santos et. al., (2020) explains that, the active participation of the inns in the execution of tourist projects, contributes to local development, through exchange of experiences and sharing of knowledge, since, designing strategies will result in the solution of complexities and local needs that establish in favor of the receiving community which, in turn, begins to create a tourist/visitor relationship as a participatory process in tourism planning.

It was also asked if the inn had already carried out any evaluation regarding the performance of the employees and as a response given by the participants it was verified that 2 (two) stated that they had already carried out an evaluation and 11 (eleven) stated that they had not carried out any

performance evaluation.

Through these responses, Carvalho (2012) emphasizes that evaluating the performance of employees is to bring the best way to know their professional profile, understand their potential and identify their possible difficulties, intended to improve productivity and results to be achieved. This is because these assessment techniques are essential not only for performance, but also to encourage collaboration and teamwork.

In the following question, it was asked if they had already carried out any training with the employees and in the answers given, it was observed that 3 (three) inns stated that they had carried out training, while 10 (ten) stated that they had not carried out training.

According to Silva Barreto; Albuquerque; Medeiros (2014) the training process with employees is to bring their preparation, aiming to deal with all the conditions involved in the execution of activities, therefore, training becomes fundamental for the internal segments of the place, as well as, a correct functioning and more assertive, because it is through these strategies that the demands and expectations are aligned to integrate all involved.

To complement the questioning, it was asked how often the inn conducts training with employees and the answers are shown in the chart below.

Graph Frequency of training with employees of the inns of Caldas Novas in the year 2022

Source: Data from the researcher (2022).

Observing the answers in the graph above, Carvalho (2012) explains that employee training must be frequent, due to the strategies that establish the important transmission of a culture of values, local politics and philosophy. Therefore, employees become aware of what is expected, resulting in improved performance, in addition to avoiding behaviors that may influence the organization. Therefore, there is an objective listed in the training that, in turn, establishes a single purpose of an efficient operation.

In the following, the participants were asked if they knew about the 360-degree assessment and it was verified that none of the participants was aware of such an assessment.

According to Silva Barreto; Albuquerque; Medeiros (2014) when defining evaluation as an instrument that can be used in employee management, aiming to monitor team or individual performance. This tool is able to analyze various segments, in order to create strategies that are capable of developing the engagement, productivity and motivation of local professionals.

It was asked how the management of the inn would define the Environment in Novas Caldas and the answers about the definitions about the management of the inn and the Environment in Caldas Novas, proved to be blunt with the actions, and there are other issues that had the slightest consideration, the need to comply with legislation, preservation and tourist activities.

According to Sartori et. al. (2014), the environment in Novas Caldas is hampered by the lack of political interest, which is a challenge that is posed to public authorities, whatever the project or program to be applied, the municipality needs sustainable development. For that, the functions of the local ecosystem, in a renewable way, must count on the contribution in the capacity of produced wealth, social balance, among other aspects that are necessary to bring social harmony. In the subsequent question, they were asked what were the difficulties encountered in maintaining the preservation of the local environment and the

answers were presented that the dissatisfaction with garbage collection as a higher priority in the difficulties, stating that the problems of Caldas Novas are related to human action, inserting this in a complex condition that needs to be reviewed through interventions or strategies, in order to further degrade the natural resources of this municipality.

According to Sousa; Barbosa (2008), the maintenance and prevention of the environment has been carried out by several public managers, in which the difficulties give more attention to those environmental complexities, starting to directly compromise the quality of life of the people of this municipality, such as the related selective collections, for example. However, depending on this local reality and the perception of each citizen, there are other issues that may be more relevant in this city, which is human awareness.

CONCLUSION

The study found that the city of Caldas Novas had a significant advance in complexity in environmental management, which is why local activities imply in the face of the natural resources of this region, implying that the management of this municipality presents fragility that impacts on the implementations and inspections of environmental policies. Noting that the municipal bodies that make up this region guide such procedures that regulate protection and prevention, however, according to economic speed, it negatively reflects several sectors, including inns and hotels.

When looking at numbers obtained from the municipal management of the environment and water resources, especially in the period between 2015-2020, there is slight progress in decision-making aimed at making public authorities available to obtain better results in managing the environment environment.

Therefore, it was observed that, during the research of theoretical references, the tourist activities of Caldas Novas, are users of thermal waters which, in turn, have several licenses that meet the dictates of legislation, Resolutions, among other

legal devices. It is noticed that there is a list of instruments that are referred to the framework of economic means that potentiate local pollution and that end up causing factors that significantly prove the environmental impact.

For all the above, it is concluded that the constant significant increase of visitors, in Caldas Novas, causes the inns to be overcrowded, overloading their basic services, noting that this floating population starts to provide an increase in demand that results in the local degradation. However, it is summarized that tourist activities directly affect this municipality, harming the daily lives of residents of this city, considering that the management of these establishments is primarily responsible for negative experiences in this territory.

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